

Revisiting Socio-economic Effects of Microcredit: A Case of Mymensingh District in Bangladesh

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Abstract

This paper explores the socio-economic impacts of microcredit in Mymensingh district of Bangladesh. Using a household survey in four sub-districts of Mymensingh, the paper finds that microcredit programs contribute to poverty reduction in this particular area by augmenting income and expenditure on consumption. The borrowers improve their dietary intakes, educational attainments, and health as well as housing conditions. Women can take part in family decision making and their authority in family increases. Borrowers' assets and net worth increase after participating microcredit program as well. There are some problems identified such as insufficient credit amount and lax monitoring by program officials. Small micro lenders are also mushrooming in Bangladesh and they charge usurious rates of interest on credit. Strong government monitoring is required to control malpractices in the micro finance market.

Keywords: Microcredit, socio-economic conditions, poverty, expenditure.

1. Introduction

Microfinance is a great innovation to remove the credit constraint faced by poor especially in the developing world. It has succeeded in reaching the poor and women who don't have access to formal financial market. Some potential poor especially women who have entrepreneurial skills but

can't initiate, maintain and expand enterprises or can't reap the benefits of their venture because of usurious rate of interest they pay to the informal money lenders for their borrowings. Therefore, the poor remain trapped in poverty (Chen and Ravallion, 2007; Yunus, 1998; Stiglitz, 1990). Microcredit comes in rescue to this trapped poor all over the world. Large body of literature supports manifold benefits of microcredit across the globe. Microcredit eradicates poverty, (Stewart et al., 2010; Pitt and Khandker, 1998) smoothen consumption (Imai and Azam, 2012), encourages female entrepreneurship (Chowdhury, 2015), reduces child labour; increases school enrolment, help formation of human capital and physical assets (Khandker and Samad, 2014b). It also enhances agricultural productivity and ensures food security (Khandker and Koolwal, 2014; Wadud, 2013). Microcredit has positive impact on various development outcomes such as venture growth, venture profitability, financial well-being, health and nutrition, education and empowerment of women (Chliova et al., 2015). However, microcredit also comes under attack for charging exorbitant rate of interest. Some scholars also challenge the success of microcredit (Morduch, 1998; Roodman and Morduch, 2014).

Microcredit program, originating in Bangladesh over three decades ago, reaches to the poor all over the world. This program has experienced spectacular growth in Bangladesh in recent years. There are debates in the microcredit discourses that microcredit market in Bangladesh has been saturated and the borrower can't draw much benefit from the borrowed fund from micro finance institutions (MFIs). Even, day by day the poor in Bangladesh is being caught in poverty trap as they are becoming over-indebted. This paper attempts to revisit the socio-economic impacts of microcredit on the poor borrowers in a particular region of Bangladesh. This paper will contribute to the microcredit literature, especially the literature of microcredit in a particular region.

2. Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to review microcredit literature in Bangladesh and to revisit the role of some renowned microcredit programs in Bangladesh. To investigate the current contribution of microcredit program to individual development of the poor, Mymensingh District of Bangladesh is chosen purposively. Specifically, this paper looks into changes in the following socio-economic indicators such as:

- ❖ Income, savings and expenditure;
- ❖ Economic solvency;
- ❖ Land ownership pattern;
- ❖ Education and training activities;
- ❖ Women's participation in decision-making;
- ❖ Health, sanitation; and
- ❖ Condition of homesteads and housing facilities.

3. Methodology

This study is entirely based on primary data. Data were collected by applying personal interview, observation and focused group discussion with the borrowers during June and July, 2015. To review literature different influential journal articles, reports have been consulted. To collect primary data a well-structured questionnaire is used and to minimize errors in data collection the questionnaire is properly pretested. To conduct this study we have selected four out of twelve upazilas (sub-district) of Mymensingh district namely Trishal, Fulbaria, Bhaluka, and Nandail randomly. We have considered two large microcredit programs namely Association of Social Advancement (ASA) and Bangladesh Rural Advancement Committee (BRAC) only. From this area we have interviewed 25 borrowing households of each program and each sub-district, a total of 200 households, randomly. List of borrowers has been collected from local microcredit offices concerned. To analyze primary data we have applied both quantitative and qualitative approaches. Some quantitative and qualitative findings are presented in simple tabular method.

3. Review of Literature

In growing body of poverty literature, it is argued that for constraint of access to financial resources the poor people remain poor and it is the main setback of their development (Chen and Ravallion, 2007; Yunus, 1998). Moreover, the poor can't reap the benefit of credit borrowed from the local traditional money lenders because of the usurious rates the lenders charge (Stiglitz, 1990). For lack of access to financial resources the poor can't not venture, maintain and further business activities. Some scholars argue that microcredit programs have paved the path of financial resources for the poor. Therefore, microcredit program removes credit constraints, enhances entrepreneurial possibilities and widens the horizon of individual development. While, others challenge the proclaimed achievement of microcredit (see Kent and Dacin, 2013; Morduch, 1999; Stewart et al., 2010; Stiglitz, 1990). Chliova et al. (2015) synthesize a total of 545 quantitative empirical findings from 90 influential studies and applying a meta-analysis come to conclusion that microcredit has positive impact on various development outcomes. Key outcomes are venture growth, venture profitability, financial well-being, health and nutrition, education and empowerment of women. They also find that microcredit is most beneficial in weak institutional settings, for instance where people have limited access to health and education or political freedom and transparency are reduced.

Microcredit has become effective way-out to lift the poor out of poverty because of high rate of return on micro investment by the poor in microenterprises. Several studies find high rate of return on microcredit rejecting the theory of poverty trap. McKenzie and Woodruff (2006) find high rate of return in the study of Mexico. The rate of return was 15 percent per month or 180 percent per year among the firms who had invested below \$200. However, the rate of return was much lower (about 3% per month) among the firms who had invested more than \$1000. Udry and Anagol (2006) studied the rate of return in the informal sector of Ghana. The authors find an exorbitant rate of return there. The real rate of return was in the range of 250 –300% per acre for the farmers who had cultivated pineapple with new technology. And the rate of return was in between of 30 -50 % for the farmer who had cultivated well-established food crop. McKenzie and Woodruff (2008) carried out a randomized experiment in Sri Lanka to analyze rate of return to capital. Four types of

treatment were given to randomly selected microenterprises. The treatments include grant of cash and in-kind capital. More than half (58%) of the grant money was invested in business. Random cash or in-kind grants increased profit rate of the microenterprises by 5 percent monthly or 60 percent annually. Stock of capital and work effort by owner of the microenterprises increased as well. Marginal rate of return for additional work effort was estimated to 4.6% to 5.3% monthly or 55% to 63% annually. These studies justify the relatively high rate of interest in microcredit compared to the formal banking credit.

Microcredit studies in Bangladesh also show positive impact on the borrower. Pitt and Khandker (1998) find that access to microcredit significantly increases consumption and reduces poverty. They study on three well renowned and nationally representative microcredit programs, namely Grameen Bank, Bangladesh Rural Advancement Committee (BRAC), and Bangladesh Rural Development Board's (BRDB) Rural Development RD-12. Their main finding is that annual household consumption expenditure increases by 18 taka for every 100 additional taka borrowed by women from these credit programs compared with 11 taka for men. However, Morduch (1998) and Roodman & Morduch (2014) cast doubt on the findings of Pitt and Khandkar (PK hereafter). Using the same dataset as used by PK but applying a different econometric model, Morduch (1998) finds that the effect on consumption of accessing to microcredit program is insignificant or even negative.

There is large body of literature finding the positive impacts of microcredit in Bangladesh. Chemin (2008), using a propensity score matching methodology, finds a lower effect than Pitt and Khandker (1998) but obtains estimates that are still positive and higher than those of Morduch (1998). Are microcredit borrowers in Bangladesh over indebted? In answer to this question, Khnadker et al. (2013) using a long panel household survey data finds that 26 percent of borrower compared to 22 percent of non-borrower are over-indebted. Growing Competition among micro finance institutions (MFI) and repeated borrowing might have been responsible for over-indebtedness among the borrowers. Khandker and Samad (2014a) also refute the allegation that microcredit borrowers in Bangladesh are trapped in poverty or debt. Rather the borrowers who have been with MFIs for the long time have made significant improvement relating to income, consumption, asset accumulation, children's schooling. These improvements are greater in the case of female borrower. However, Islam and Choe (2013) find that household participation in microcredit may increase child labour and reduce school enrolment. Access to microcredit has a significant positive impact on women entrepreneurship in Bangladesh (Chowdhury 2015). Drawing upon the nationally representative household panel with four rounds from 1997 to 2004 Imai and Azam (2012) find that positive effects of general microfinance loans and loans for productive purposes on income, food consumption and women's Body Mass Index. Growth of food consumption indicates poverty reduction. Since microcredit programs in Bangladesh are increasing day by day, the market for credit may be saturated and village diseconomies can take place which in turn may reduce credit benefits among the borrowers. Drawing upon a long panel survey data spanning over 20 years Khandker and Samad (2014b) confirm that credit benefit is still continuing contributing to the welfare of poor borrowers especially the women. Membership to multiple credit programs helps raise asset and net worth rather than contributing to indebtedness. Some argue that microcredit is also a poverty trap because the rate of interest is usurious and the borrowers use fresh borrowing to repay the existing loan. However, Woutersen and Khandker (2014) reject the

hypothesis of poverty trap. Agricultural households' participation to microcredit program has profound impact on agricultural productivity in Bangladesh as well. This impact is much higher in the household with lower land ownings, raising agricultural income from activities such as livestock rearing that require less land (Khandker and Koolwal 2014). Study of Wadud (2013) in four northern districts also confirms the link between microcredit participation and agricultural farm performance and food security in Bangladesh.

4. Brief Account of Socio-economic Characteristics of the Respondents

On the occupational status, most of the respondents (93.5 percent) are housewife. Women are the main borrower in the surveyed area. A small percent of respondents (3 percent) reported their occupation as petty business. Almost half of the respondents (about 46 percent) have primary education, while about 16 percent have studied up to junior secondary school qualification. A quarter of respondents do not have any educational qualification. Most of the households (61 percent) are with single earning member, while 28 percent of households report two earning members.

5. Major findings of the Study

In this section major findings of the impact of microcredit on the socio-economic conditions of the respondents are explained. We consider before-after comparison of changes due to participating microcredit programs.

5.1.Changes in yearly Income

In this study we consider changes in yearly income of respondents' family as main economic impact of microcredit. We asked the respondents about their level of yearly income before and after participating microcredit program. Table 1 reports changes in the range of yearly income before and after participating in any microcredit program.

Table 1: Changes In Yearly Income

Categories	Before		After	
	Number of respondents	% of respondents	Number of respondents	% of respondents
Below 50,000	2	1.0	0.00	0.00
50,000-100,000	58	29.0	17	8.5
100,000-500,000	140	70.0	183	91.5
Above 5 lakh	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total	200	100	200	100

Source: Field survey and author's calculation

Among 200 responding households, 70 percent had yearly income in between BDT 100,000 and 500,000 before participating microcredit program. But after participating in microcredit program almost 92 percent household's yearly income reach to the range of BDT 100,000-500,000. This income statistics indicates that after receiving credit from the micro finance institutions (MFI) a significant percent of the households' income increases.

5.2 Expenditure Pattern

Table 2 reports expenditure pattern of the responding households. About half (44%) of the household's yearly per capita expenditure falls on the category of BDT 20,000-30,000, while 53 percent households' per capita yearly expenditure exceeds BDT 30,000. A good portion of total expenditure goes to the head of buying food items. They also spend some amount on education and health care. Most of the respondents report that after participating microcredit their yearly per capita expenditure increases. Per capita expenditure on education and health care increase as well. This upward trend of expenditure confirms poverty reduction among microcredit participants.

**Table 2 :Yearly Expenditure Pattern
(After participating Microcredit Program)**

Per Capita Expenditure		
Categories	Number of respondents	% of respondents
Below 20,000	6	3
20,000-30,000	87	43.5
Above 30,000	107	53.5
Total	200	100
Per Capita Expenditure on Food		
Categories	Number of respondents	% of respondents
Below 10,000	1	0.5
10,000-15,000	40	20
Above 15,000	159	79.5
Total	200	100
Per Capita Expenditure on Education		
Categories	Number of respondents	% of respondents
0 – 5,000	141	70.5
Above 5,000	59	29.5
Total	200	100
Per Capita Expenditure on Health		
Categories	Number of respondents	% of respondents
0 – 2,000	157	78.5
Above 2,000	43	21.5
Total	200	100

Source: field survey and author's calculation

5.3 Economic Solvency after receiving Credit

Generally, poor people borrow money from any sources to change their economic plight. However, some people borrow money to meet one-time needs such as medical treatment, arrangement of wedding ceremony for siblings or building or repairing households and so on. In that case economic solvency may not persist in the long run as the borrower has to repay the borrowing. Those who invest the borrowed fund for income generation can gain economic solvency in the long run. We asked the respondent if they are economically solvent after receiving loan from MFIs. About 89 percent households respond affirmatively. They can afford dietary intake, send children to school and have better access to health care (Table 3).

Table 3: Economic SOLVENCY After Receiving Loan

Category	Number of respondents	% of respondents
Yes	177	88.5
No	23	11.5
Total	200	100.0

Source: Field survey and author's calculation

5.4.Savings

Microcredit program encourages poor borrowers to save more. Borrowing from MFIs requires compulsory saving with MFIs. Therefore, the borrowers' saving mentality changes positively after the involvement with the microcredit programs. Respondents confirm that their per capita savings also increases, albeit the saving amount is very low (Table 4).

Table 4: Yearly per capita Saving (after participating Microcredit)

Categories	Number of respondents	% of respondents
0 – 2,000	141	70.5
Above 2,000	59	29.5
Total	200	100

Source: Field survey and author's calculation

As far as saving instrument is concerned, most of the households save with the program only, while others save with both program and formal bank.

5.5.Ownership of Land

Some studies show that with the participation of microcredit the borrower accumulates assets and increase net worth (see Khandker and Samad 2014a, Khandker and Samad 2014b).To look into asset position of the borrower we asked about the change in landowning. Our findings also confirm that participation of microcredit program increase net asset. However, the change is meager in our study. Only 2.5 percent of the households experience gain in landowning. The fact is that monetary value of a piece of land is much higher compared to the small amount of credit that borrower can draw from MFIs. With focus group discussion the respondents report that although they cannot afford buying land, their net worth increase in the form of other assets such as consumer durables, jewellery and agricultural equipment.

Table 5: Ownership of Land

Categories	Before		After	
	Number of respondents	% of respondents	Number of respondents	% of respondents
0-1.99 acre	188	94.0	183	91.5
2- 2.99 acre	12	6.0	17	8.5
Above 5 acre	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total	200	100	200	100

Source: Field survey and author's calculation

5.6 Structure of main House

Many of the poor draw microcredit from MFIs to improve their housing condition or spend profit--gained from the micro investment--on housing facilities. Better dwelling place in the rural Bangladesh is an important status symbol. Table 6 presents before--after comparison in structure of main house of the poor borrowers.

Table 6: Structure of main House

Categories			Before		After	
			Number of respondents	% of respondents	Number of respondents	% of respondents
House Type	Floor	Paka	14	7.0	30	15.0
		Kacha	186	93.0	170	85.0
		Total	200	100.0	200	100.0
	Wall	Brick built	10	5.0	25	12.5
		Soil	12	6.0	8	4.0
		Straw	29	14.5	1	.5
		Tin	142	71.0	164	82.0
		Bamboo	5	2.5	1	.5
		Others	2	1.0	1	.5
		Total	200	100.0	200	100.0
	Roof	Paka	5	2.5	10	5.0
		Tin	164	82.0	188	94.0
		Straw	29	14.5	0.00	0.0 0
		Others	2	1.0	2	1.0
		Total	200	100.0	200	100.0

Source: Field survey and author's calculation

Among the 200 respondents, 7% lived in paka (pavement) floored houses and 93% lived in kacha (earthen) floored houses before participating microcredit but after the participation 15% live in paka floored houses and 85% live in kacha floored houses. Before participating microcredit programs, wall of the main house of the respondents was with brick (5%), soil (6%) straw (14.5%), tin (71%), bamboo (5%) and others (1%). After participating microcredit the wall of the main house improves. The respondents informed that microcredit is beneficial to changing their housing condition even though they do not invest the credit on any other productive purposes. If they spend credit for building new house or improving existing house, they fell forced to save for credit repayment installments, otherwise they wouldn't have saved a lot.

5.7. Education

Education is an essential tool for human development. Besides the government initiatives, some MFIs are engaged in education program in Bangladesh. Education programs of BRAC and ASA help the borrowing households in attaining education. BRAC runs informal preprimary school in every nook and corner of Bangladesh. Many of the MFIs have concessional loan scheme for education along with free distribution of educational materials. Table 7 presents number of households receiving or not the educational benefit offered by the concerned MFIs in our study.

Table 7: Gaining Educational Benefit

Response	Number of respondents	% of respondents
Yes	24	12.0
No	176	88.0
Total	200	100.0

Source: Field survey and author's calculation

Among 200 respondents only 12% respondent's children can receive educational facilities, while 88% respondents cannot receive the facilities in the study area.

5.8. Sanitation Facilities

After the operation of MFIs and non-governments organizations (NGO) Bangladesh has achieved commendable success in attaining sanitation related improvements. Some NGOs distribute sanitary goods freely. Other NGOs have health awareness program that also stimulate using healthy sanitation. We investigate sanitation related improvement among the borrowers and find that a significant number of respondents (90 %) improve condition of their toilets(Table 8)

Table 8: Sanitation Facilities

Categories	Before		After	
	Number of respondents	% of respondents	Number of respondents	% of respondents
Kacha	160	80.0	102	51.0
Paka	27	13.5	90	45.0
No latrine	13	6.5	8	4.0
Total	200	100	200	100

Source: Field survey and author's calculation

5.9. Mobile Phone Facilities

Penetration of mobile phone technology in Bangladesh has far-reaching effects on the livelihoods of the rural poor. For lack of proper information market failure can take place leading to welfare loss of the poor microenterprises. Jensen (2007) shows that penetration and adoption of mobile phone facilities in the fishing industry of South India lead to welfare gain for both the fishermen and the wholesalers. Adoption of mobile phones is associated with a dramatic reduction in price dispersion, the complete elimination of waste and near-perfect adherence to Law of One Price in

that fishing industry. We also look into whether adoption of mobile phones increases among poor borrower or not.

Table 9: Mobile Phone Facilities

Response	Before		After	
	Number of respondents	% of respondents	Number of respondents	% of respondents
Yes	67	33.5	187	93.5
No	133	66.5	13	6.5
Total	200	100	200	100

Source: Field survey and author's calculation

Table 9 expresses that among 200 respondents, 67 (33.5%) respondents had and 133(66.5%) had not a mobile phone before participating microcredit, whereas 187(93.5%) have and 13(6.5%) have not a mobile phone after participating microcredit programs. This finding reveals that microcredit may have positive impact on the income enhancement of the poor through adoption of mobile phones.

5.10. Participation in Family Decision Making

In our survey most of borrowers are women and most them do not spend the credit directly. They hand over the credit amount to the sole bread earner--husband or son. Since women borrow the fund, they have much role on the decision of how to invest the amount. Women also report that their participation in family decision making increases after involving with MFIs. Table 10 shows that 77 percent of respondents confirm that after participating microcredit women get increased authority in the family.

Table 10 : Women's Authority in Households

Category	Number of respondents	% of respondents
Yes	154	77.0
No	46	23.0
Total	200	100.0

Source: Field survey and author's calculation

6. Concluding Remarks

In this study we attempt to investigate the socio-economic impacts of microcredit in a particular region of Bangladesh. A growing body of literature supports that microcredit has multifaceted impact on the individual development of the poor in Bangladesh. Individual development, in turn, results overall development of Bangladesh as well. To revisit the role of microcredit we select Mymensingh district and conduct a random survey in four sub-districts under Mymensingh. Our findings also confirm the profound socio-economic impact of microcredit on the poor borrowers in this particular area. Respondents report that after participating microcredit they experience increase in income and expenditure. A good chunk of increased income is spent on education, health and nutritious food. Obviously, this increased expenditure contributes to formation of human capital

and reduction of poverty. Borrowers also improve the condition of their dwelling places and sanitary facilities. Women's empowerment is also discernible in this area as women can participate in family decision making process.

On the flip side, most of the respondents claim that the credit amount is not sufficient to run relatively larger enterprises and that is why some of them participate in multiple microcredit programs. None of the female borrowers run any kind of enterprises. It is reported that in case of loan default MFIs put excessive pressure on the borrower which also bar some poor from entering a microcredit program. With loopholes of MFI monitoring, some borrowers take credit showing false reason and consume entire amount without investing in any kind of productive activities. Consequently, they become defaulters which creates problems to others in a group based micro borrowing. It is common allegation against MFIs of charging high rate of interest but the borrower is not informed about true rates. It is found in our survey that 69 percent respondents do not know the exact rate of interest at which they borrow.

Since microcredit program is still beneficial to the poor and hardcore poor in Bangladesh it's coverage should be widen, especially in the poverty-stricken regions. Credit amount also needs to be increased as some entrepreneurial borrowers require more credit. Program monitoring should be stricter so that the poor invest in any productive activates otherwise they become defaulters which creates problems to group lending. Microcredit programs are also mushrooming in Bangladesh and some small MFI charge usurious rate of interest like the informal money lender. In this regards, government monitoring on MFIs should be beefed up.

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